

New Mercury-ammonia Compounds.

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The action of ammonia upon various simple and some double or complex mercury-salts like potassium mercuric iodide and sodium mercuric nitrite, etc., has been studied by various investigators from a very early time. A very large number of complex mercury-ammonia compounds have been described. But the subject is still far from being exhausted. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of some new ammoniacal compounds of mercury and with the description of some interesting reactions. By the action of ammonia and ammonium carbonate upon mercuric chlor-iodide under different conditions, the following compounds have been obtained :

Mercuric brom-iodide, on the other hand, gave only more or less pure dimercurammonium bromide. By the action of potassium thiocyanate upon infusible white precipitate a new mercury-ammonium thiocyanate of the formula NH_3SCN has been obtained. Action of potassium chromate upon infusible white precipitate, on the other hand, gave rise to the formation of a chromate of Millon's

base. Potassium bromide gave dimercur-ammonium bromide and potassium iodide gave the iodide of Millon's base. An arsenate of Millon's base which has not been described in the literature has been obtained by the action of ammonia upon mercuric arsenate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Ammonia upon Mercuric Chlor-iodide.—

A solution of mercuric chlor-iodide was prepared by saturating mercuric chloride solution with mercuric iodide. The solution was then added drop by drop with constant stirring to a large excess of strong ammonia. An orange-yellow precipitate was formed, it was filtered and washed first with ammonia, then with water and finally with alcohol. The substance was then dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

The substance was soluble in hydrochloric acid but not in sulphuric acid and gave ammonia with caustic soda. On heating in a dry test tube, ammonia was given off and a sublimate consisting of mercurous chloride, mercuric iodide, ammonium chloride and some metallic mercury was formed. Several samples were prepared under varying conditions of temperature and concentration of the chlor-iodide solution and gave the same composition. The same compound was also obtained from an excess of boiling ammonia solution.

Analysis :

Found : Hg=85·7, 85·86, 85·1, 85·1, 85·4 per cent.

Cl =6·37, 6·37, 6·3, 6·34 per cent.

I =4·01, 3·91 per cent.

N =3·26, 3·17 per cent.

$6\text{NHg}_2\text{Cl}$, NHg_2I , $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Hg=85·52,

Cl =6·5, I=3·9, N=3 01 per cent.

It may also be represented as a triple compound of dimercur-ammonium chloride, chloride of Millon's base and iodide of Millon's base.

It should, however, be pointed out that only infusible white precipitate is obtained by the addition of mercuric chloride to a large excess of ammonia.

Secondly, a white precipitate was formed by adding dilute ammonia to an excess of the chlor-iodide solution; addition of ammonia must be stopped before the precipitate showed any yellow tinge; hence the mercury salt should always be in large excess. The substance thus prepared contained no iodine. The precipitate was washed with alcohol and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

It was soluble in acids, gave ammonia with caustic soda or ammonium bromide. Dry ignition decomposed it into ammonia, mercurous chloride and water.

Analysis:

Found: Hg = 78.7, 79.02 per cent.

Cl = 16.23, 16.17 per cent. N = 3.46 per cent.

$4\text{NH}_2\text{HgCl}, \text{NHg}_3\text{Cl}, 2\text{HgCl}_2$ requires Hg = 80; Cl = 16.1 and N = 3.5 per cent.

Action of Ammonium Carbonate upon Mercuric Chlor-iodide.

To an excess of pure ammonium carbonate solution, a solution of mercuric chlor-iodide was added drop by drop. The precipitate first formed soon redissolved; with the addition of more mercuric salt a permanent white precipitate was formed. It was washed first with dilute ammonium carbonate solution, then with alcohol and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The substance tended to decompose on treatment with water turning

yellow. On heating in a dry test tube, the substance first turned yellow, partly fused and then decomposed with evolution of ammonia and gave a white sublimate of Hg_2Cl_2 . It was soluble in acids, gave off ammonia with caustic soda and ammonium bromide.

Analysis :

Found : $\text{Hg} = 71.4, 71.7$; $\text{Cl} = 19.52, 19.41$.

$\text{N} = 7.504$.

$\text{NH}_2\text{HgCl}, \text{HgCl}_2, 2\text{NH}_3$, requires $\text{Hg} = 71.9$; $\text{Cl} = 19.1$
and $\text{N} = 7.5$ per cent.

The substance appears to be a double compound of one molecule of infusible white precipitate and one molecule of fusible white precipitate. The presence of the latter was indicated by its ready decomposition on warming with water with the development of a yellow tinge and the passage of ammonium chloride in the filtrate.

On the other hand, when ammonium carbonate solution was added to an excess of the mercuric salt, a white precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, mother liquor drained off by strong suction, washed with alcohol and then dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

The substance was soluble in acids, on heating in a dry test tube it decomposed with evolution of ammonia and gave a white sublimate of mercurous chloride.

Analysis :

Found : $\text{Hg} = 78.6, 78.9, 78.45$; $\text{Cl} = 17.5, 17.6,$
 17.6 ; $\text{N} = 2.9, 2.6, 2.6$.

$\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}, 2 \text{HgCl}_2, \text{NH}_3$, requires $\text{Hg} = 79.3$; $\text{Cl} = 17.6$,
 $\text{N} = 2.77$ per cent.

It should however be mentioned here that by the action of ammonium carbonate solution upon mercuric chloride solution alone, infusible precipitate is always obtained, which is again soluble in an excess of ammonium carbonate solution.

As these compounds were all insoluble in water, nitric and sulphuric acids and incompletely decomposed by alkali and as some of them contained both chlorine and iodine, some difficulties arose as regards their analysis which were overcome in the following way:—

Mercury was estimated as mercuric sulphide after dissolving the substance in hydrochloric acid. Estimation of chlorine was made by mixing the substance with six times its weight of anhydrous sodium carbonate in a porcelain crucible and heating the latter slowly with the lid in position on an asbestos ring—Mercury escaped by vaporisation and chlorine remained fixed as sodium chloride. If iodine were present, a part of it vaporised as mercuric iodide and a part was fixed as sodium iodide. After expelling all the mercury, the mass was acidified with nitric acid, treated with ammoniacal silver nitrate solution, any iodine present being precipitated, the solution was filtered, acidified with nitric acid, silver chloride was reprecipitated and weighed as AgCl . Iodine was estimated as follows:—the substance was dissolved in cold hydrochloric acid and the mercury was precipitated as mercury sulphide and then the filtrate was rendered alkaline with sodium carbonate and evaporated to dryness. The mass was then treated with ferric alum and sulphuric acid, iodine was distilled, absorbed in potassium iodide solution and then titrated with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method.

Action of Ammonia upon Mercuric Brom-iodide.—

In the first place a solution of mercuric brom-iodide prepared by saturating a solution of mercuric bromide with mercuric iodide was added drop by drop to an excess of ammonia. The solution first turned yellow, then reddish brown and with the addition of more mercuric salt a reddish brown precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed with ammonia water and then with alcohol and dried in vacuo over strong sulphuric acid.

The substance was soluble in hydrochloric acid; when heated in a dry test tube it decomposed into mercuric iodide, mercurous bromide and some metallic mercury but gave no ammonia.

Analysis of different samples showed variable composition; the substance seemed to be a mixture of NHg_2Br with a little NHg_2I .

On the other hand, when ammonia was added to an excess of the mercuric brom-iodide solution, a yellow precipitate was formed. On examination it was found to be almost identical with NHg_2Br usually obtained by the action of ammonia upon boiling mercuric bromide solution. The same compound NHg_2Br was also obtained when ammonium carbonate solution was added to an excess of mercuric brom-iodide solution. This compound was soluble in an excess of ammonium carbonate solution.

Action of some Potassium Salts upon Infusible White Precipitate.—

It has been shown (Gazzetta, 1893, 22, 11,557) that when the mercuri-ammonium salts are heated with solution of potassium or sodium salts, they are decomposed with the evolution of ammonia and formation of mercuric salts (Kane, Ann. Chim, Phys.; Rammelsberg,

Poggendorf's Annal. Phys. Chem., 48, 182). We studied this reaction again and found that by the action of potassium salts, an intermediate compound was first formed. In most cases this compound was very stable and went into solution when boiled with a large excess of the reagent.

Action of Potassium Sulphocyanide Solution upon Infusible White Precipitate and the Formation of Dehydrated Sulphocyanide of Millon's Base.—

A freshly prepared white precipitate was treated with a strong solution of potassium sulphocyanide, first in the cold and then heated on the water-bath for about three hours with constant stirring. A large amount of ammonia was evolved and the residue turned yellow. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

The substance was soluble in large excess of potassium sulphocyanide after boiling for some time and evolved a large amount of ammonia. It was also soluble in acids. On heating in a dry test tube it exploded forming a black deposit of mercuric sulphide, a mirror of metallic mercury and gave out a garlic smell.

Analysis :

Found: Hg=84.6, 84.6 ; S=6.7, 6.78 ;

N=6.28, 6.24 per cent.

NHg, SCN requires Hg=84.8 ; S=6.76 and

N=6 per cent.

The filtrate after the separation of the yellow product was found to contain free ammonia and CNS', Cl', ON', K⁺ and Hg⁺⁺ ions. On allowing the solution to crystallise after evaporation the double salt Hg(SCN)₂, KSCN mixed with some Hg(SCN)₂, NH₄SCN were obtained.

The reaction that occurs may be represented as follows:—

This compound has not been described by any previous worker and corresponds to the analogous compounds NHg_2Cl , NHg_2Br etc.

Action of Potassium Chromate upon Infusible White Precipitate and the Formation of Chromate of Millon's Base.—

Freshly prepared white precipitate was treated with a strong solution of potassium chromate on the water-bath or about 12 hours with constant stirring; ammonia was evolved and a greenish yellow product was obtained. It was then filtered, washed and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid.

On heating in a dry test tube the substance decomposed into mercurous and mercuric chromate and water but gave no ammonia.

Analysis :

Found : Hg = 81.3, 82.3 ; Cr = 5.7, 5.3 ;

The reaction that occurs may be represented as follows:—

The same compound has been described by Hensgen who obtained it by dissolving mercuric oxide in ammonium bichromate and then heating the solution with excess of ammonia. (Hensgen, Rec. Trav. Chem., 1887, 5, 187.)

The infusible white precipitate when treated in a similar way with potassium bromide solution avoiding a large excess, a yellow product soluble in excess of potassium bromide solution was obtained. This was found to be identical with NHg_2Br .

Similarly the first action of potassium iodide solution upon infusible white precipitate was found to cause the production of iodide of Millon's base which dissolved in an excess of potassium iodide solution evolving a large amount of ammonia.

Potassium arsenite, on the other hand, reduced the infusible white precipitate and metallic mercury was separated. No perceptible reaction was observed in the cases of sulphate, phosphate, fluoride, borate and arseniate of potassium.

Preparation of Arseniate of Millon's Base.

No arsenical mercury ammonium compound has been described by any worker. A compound which may be regarded as an arseniate of Millon's base was prepared in the following manner. Freshly prepared mercuric arseniate was digested with ammonia when the yellow mercuric arseniate turned white. It was then filtered,

washed with dilute ammonia, then with alcohol and dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid. A slightly yellowish product was obtained after drying.

Analysis :

Found : Hg=79.3, 79.7 ; As=5.27 ; N=3.09.

requires Hg=80.5 ; As=5.0 ; N=2.84 per cent.

The reaction occurs as follows :—

Action of Sulphur Dioxide upon Infusible White Precipitate.—

When sulphur dioxide gas was passed into water in which freshly prepared infusible white precipitate was suspended, the latter went into solution which on evaporation gave a crystalline substance of the composition

$\text{HgSO}_3, \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$.

HgSO_3 formed dissolved in NH_4Cl giving the double salt.

The same compound has also been described by Ruff and co-workers (Zeit. Anorg. Chem., 1920, 114, 203). But the mechanism of the action represented by the authors of the above paper is rather unusual and has no strong

evidence in support of it. It was represented as follows:—

This is a rather far-fetched representation of the case.

It is however a known fact that insoluble mercuric salts easily dissolve in ammonium salt solutions and form double salts.

Action of Nitrous Acid upon Infusible White Precipitate.—

When N_2O_5 is passed into cold water containing freshly prepared infusible white precipitate in suspension, the latter dissolved and the solution on evaporation under reduced pressure gave double salt of mercuric chloride with ammonium nitrite mixed with a little nitrate. The substance was never obtained pure as ammonium nitrite in solution began to decompose on concentrating the solution.

Action of Mercuric Chloride upon Zinc or Cadmium Ammonium Chloride.—

Zinc or cadmium ammonium chloride solution was prepared by saturating an ammonium chloride solution with the hydroxides of the metals. To this solution a solution of mercuric chloride was added. A white crystalline precipitate was obtained.

The precipitate on heating in a dry test tube, fused and decomposed with the evolution of a large amount of ammonia forming a white sublimate of calomel. No zinc or cadmium was found in the product. It turned yellow with water. That is, it behaved in every respect like fusible white precipitate.

An analysis of the product confirmed this view and the substance was found to be identical with the fusible white precipitate. Action of ammonia upon mercuric chloride solution alone gives however under all circumstances only the infusible white precipitate.

The reaction can be represented as follows :—

where Me = Zn or Cd.

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